

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE SOURCES OF GOLD AND AGARWOOD IN ĐÀNG TRONG (COCHINCHINA) AND THEIR ROLE IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE HỘI AN TRADING PORT IN THE 17TH–18TH CENTURIES (VIET NAM)

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Abstract

Hội An trading port was one of the most renowned ports in Đàng Trong (Cochinchina), especially during the 17th and 18th centuries. It was a major center of commercial exchange connecting countries from East to West, as well as a place of interaction among diverse cultures, languages, and ethnic groups, including indigenous Cham people, Vietnamese, Chinese, Japanese, Portuguese, Indians, and others. The economic and cultural development of Hội An trading port in the 17th–18th centuries created a vibrant international port. Imported goods were quite diverse, such as handicrafts, while exported goods in particular generated enormous profits for the Nguyễn Lords. Export commodities at Hội An included talc, cosmetic powder, amber, gemstones, pearls, bird's nests, areca nuts, and especially gold and agarwood. These two commodities became the backbone of the Đàng Trong (Cochinchina) economy in its commercial relations with countries around the world, contributing to an unprecedented level of prosperity for the Đàng Trong economy under the Nguyễn Lords in the 17th–18th centuries.

Keywords: *gold, agarwood, Hội An trading port, export commodities of Đàng Trong (Cochinchina) Top of Form*

1. Introduction

Since the 15th century, Quảng Nam was a sparsely populated region. By the late 16th century, as Western commerce increasingly shifted toward the East and the Ming dynasty's maritime trade ban on Southeast Asian countries was lifted in 1567, Japanese and Chinese merchants found no place more favorable than Hội An for trading goods, as commercial exchanges between the two countries were in demand but prohibited by their respective governments. Consequently, Hội An became fertile ground for merchants to conduct trade and exchange goods.

During this same period, the open-door policy of the Nguyễn Lords met the urgent needs of a number of Japanese merchants who had been expelled by the Japanese shogunate in the early 17th century. Meanwhile, Chinese merchants also sought to reside and trade in Hội An. Ships could enter Hội An not only through Cửa Đại but also via Cửa Hàn through the Cổ Cò River (Lộ Cảnh Giang). From the Thanh Chiêm administrative center of Quảng Nam to Hội An, the waterway system via the Thu Bồn–Vĩnh Điện rivers was only about 10 km, while the distance from Cù Lao Chàm to Cửa Đại was merely 18 km. For these reasons, Hội An became the most important commercial hub of Đàng Trong.

The development of the economy at Hội An trading port depended fundamentally on the availability of commodities. Foreign merchants from England, France, Portugal, the Netherlands, and India came here to buy and exchange goods. In addition to popular commodities favored by foreign traders such as areca nuts, bird's nests, and silk, gold and agarwood were the two core export products of Hội An trading port in the 17th–18th centuries. Where did these commodities originate, and what varieties did they include? What roles did

gold and agarwood play in the economic development of Hội An trading port in the 17th-18th centuries?

2. Content

The greatest achievement of the land reclamation efforts in Thuận Hóa under the Nguyễn Lords was the transformation of what had once been regarded as an “inhospitable land of Ô Châu,” with its harsh climate—“spring and summer were often hot, while autumn and winter were usually rainy” (Dương Văn An, 2009, p. 40)—into a prosperous region and the political center of the Nguyễn Lords in Đàng Trong. As described, “the land of Thuận-Quảng in the north is bordered by the Hoành Sơn Mountains and the Linh Giang (Giang River), a rugged terrain where the mountains yield gold and iron, and the sea abounds in salted fish” (Phan Khoang, 2009, p. 127).

The range of export and import commodities at Hội An trading port was extremely rich, including spices and local products from various regions. Thanks to its favorable geographical location and the dense river network surrounding the port, which facilitated transportation by boat, goods of all kinds were concentrated there. In *Phủ biên tạp lục*, Lê Quý Đôn wrote: “All products produced in the prefectures of Thăng Hoa, Điện Bàn, Quy Nhơn, Bình Khang, and the Nha Trang administrative area, whether transported by waterway or overland, by boat or by horse, were gathered at Hội An wharf. Therefore, merchants from the North congregated here to trade and return to their countries; nevertheless, the most vigorous commercial route was still the relationship between the two ports of Hội An and Thanh Hà” (Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences – Institute of History, 2007, p. 295).

Imported goods into Đàng Trong mainly came from China, Japan, Portugal, the Netherlands, and Siam, and included consumer handicrafts, fine arts products, medicinal items, and foodstuffs. These foods

included “tea leaves, oranges, lemons, pears, apples, vermicelli cakes, wheat flour, salted olives, Thai oil (a type of pickled cabbage from China), salted eggs, ginger paste, sweet soybean paste, peanuts, golden needle vegetables, wood ear mushrooms, and shiitake mushrooms” (Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences – Institute of History, 2007, p. 296).

Portuguese ships arriving in 1775 brought copperware, iron goods, lead, caustic soda, and jewelry. As Quảng Nam and Thuận Hóa had no copper mines, “Japan exported mined copper; every year when Japanese ships arrived, it was purchased at a price of 45 *quan* per 100 *cân*. As for ships from Shanghai, Fujian, and Guangdong carrying red copper, they were also required to declare it so that it could be purchased at the prescribed price” (Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences - Institute of History, 2007, p. 278).

Japanese goods favored in Hội An included silver ingots, leather fabrics, various types of gemstones, handicrafts, sewing needles, and similar items (Đỗ Bang, 1996, p. 62). The wide variety and large quantity of imported goods indicate a prosperous economy in Đàng Trong, as well as a high standard of living and a refined aesthetic taste among its people. As observed by contemporary accounts: “They readily develop a fondness for the curious objects of other lands; as a result, they value and purchase at excessively high prices many items that elsewhere are of little worth, such as combs, sewing needles, bracelets, pearl earrings, and women’s ornaments. I still remember a Portuguese who brought from Macao to Đàng Trong a box of sewing needles worth only about 30 ducats, yet sold it for more than a thousand” (Borri, 1931, p. 333).

Export goods consisted of agricultural products, handicrafts, as well as forest and marine products. Among them, agarwood and gold were particularly prominent commodities: agarwood was described as “a kind of wood regarded in many places as the most precious of all valuables” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 68), while gold was noted with the observation that “Đàng Trong has many precious metal mines, especially gold mines” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 68). The Hội An trading port thus brought together all the necessary and sufficient conditions of an international port, with a diverse range of commodities. Gold and agarwood were the most sought-after goods among foreign merchants and made significant contributions to the development of Hội An trading port in the 17th-18th centuries.

2.1. Origins and Classification of Gold and Agarwood in Đàng Trong

2.1.1. Origins and Classification of Gold

According to geologists, gold is a metallic element that appears yellow in solid form; in its powdered state, 100% pure gold may appear black, ruby-red, or purplish when finely cut. It is the most malleable and ductile of metals. Gold is formed through geological processes in which water carrying high concentrations of carbon dioxide, silicon dioxide, and several other necessary substances contributes to its creation. Subsequently, aftershocks or earthquakes cause fractures to widen, leading to a sudden drop in pressure; the water rapidly evaporates, and any gold particles present in the

liquid precipitate almost immediately. Gold has excellent thermal and electrical conductivity and is not affected by air. It is chemically resistant to heat, humidity, oxygen, and most corrosive substances; therefore, it is well suited for minting coins and making jewelry.

From a geographical perspective, Đàng Trong lies entirely within the transitional zone between two major geological tectonic blocks: the Kon Tum massif and the Truong Son folded zone. Movements within these geological structures created a wide range of mineral deposits beneath the land of Quảng and Đàng Trong, resulting in abundant and diverse mineral resources.

The French merchant Pierre Poivre, who lived in Hội An for nearly 15 years, recorded the following observation: “In Đàng Trong one finds a great deal of alluvial gold... This type of gold is usually panned from streams flowing down from the mountains. I have seen pure gold ingots composed of grains the size of medium rings. Local merchants possess some of it, but the lord has a great deal. Foreign traders who come to do business in Đàng Trong take back with them a considerable amount of gold” (Poivre, 1884, pp. 324-337).

Gold was collected in the form of fine grains or small nuggets, then smelted into ingots and sold in markets like other commodities. “Đàng Trong is a land of gold; the gold here is among the finest, most beautiful, and purest in the world” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 233).

Among the various export commodities sent to other countries-including forest products, aquatic and marine products, and handicrafts-metal goods, especially raw gold, were highly favored by foreign markets (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 234). The ratio of imported and exported goods at Hội An trading port was as follows: imported goods consisted of handicrafts (55.68%), processed foodstuffs (41.87%), and pharmaceuticals (2.45%); exported goods included forest, terrestrial, and marine specialties (48%), agricultural products, foodstuffs, and handicrafts (27%), metals (12%), and pharmaceuticals (3%) (Đỗ Bang, 1996, p. 66).

2.1.2. Agarwood

Agarwood is the resinous formation of the *Aquilaria* (gió) tree. According to traditional explanations, it is believed that “heavenly fragrance carried by the wind settles onto the tree trunk, initially adhering to the bark and then gradually penetrating into the wood. Through the tree’s resin, this fragrance is transformed and spreads throughout the tree. Over time, the wood absorbs the fragrance and becomes agarwood. Agarwood then turns into *kỳ nam* due to bird droppings falling onto it or the attachment of a certain type of fungus” (Quách Tấn, 2019, p. 377). Others suggest that “the gió tree producing agarwood is like an oyster producing pearls. When branches, trunks, or roots are injured, the tree’s resin accumulates to resist the damage. After the wound heals, the resin remains, gradually altering the nature of the wood and forming agarwood. Where a large amount of resin accumulates, it becomes *kỳ*; where less resin accumulates, it becomes ordinary agarwood” (Quách Tấn, 2019, p. 378).

However, not all gió trees produce agarwood. Only trees growing deep in the forest, with weathered

trunks and swollen nodules resembling intestinal bulges or banana stems, contain agarwood. Forests with agarwood often emit a faint fragrance. Many people believe that agarwood is a gift of the Holy Mother Thiên Y A Na, bestowed upon those whom she allows to find it.

Agarwood is generally divided into two main categories: *kỳ* (or *kỳ nam*) and *trâm* (ordinary agarwood). *Kỳ nam* is said to originate from the *bầu giở* tree, while *trâm* comes from *giở lưỡn trâu* or *giở cam*. In essence, however, *kỳ nam* is agarwood with a high oil content, whereas *trâm* is agarwood with a lower oil content (Quách Tấn, 2019, p. 374). In trees containing agarwood, *kỳ nam* is always present, and in trees containing *kỳ nam*, agarwood is found surrounding or adjacent to it.

Kỳ nam and agarwood are easily distinguished by their physical characteristics and fragrance. Agarwood is hard and heavy, with a bitter taste, while *kỳ nam* is light and soft, possessing a complex taste of sourness, spiciness, sweetness, and bitterness. Agarwood has a rich, lingering aroma, whereas *kỳ nam* emits a refined, delicate scent. The smoke of agarwood curls and disperses, while the smoke of *kỳ nam* rises straight upward and high. In traditional medicine, agarwood is used to regulate and lower *qi*, whereas *kỳ nam* is used to treat ailments such as cold-induced disorders, bronchitis, and abdominal pain, with notable effectiveness. Agarwood and *kỳ nam* may be compared respectively to crystal and diamond in terms of value.

Both agarwood and *kỳ nam* are further classified into several types. *Kỳ* is divided into four grades with clearly defined values: “first white, second green, third yellow, fourth black.” *Kỳ nam*, widely used in medicine, was highly favored by Chinese, Japanese, and other merchants. Agarwood is divided into four types: *trâm mắt kiến* (ant-eye agarwood), *trâm rễ* (root agarwood), *trâm mắt tử* (formed on branches), and *trâm tót* (formed in the trunk) (Quách Tấn, 2019, p. 377).

2.2. Sites of Gold and Agarwood Exploitation in Đàng Trong

2.2.1. Sites of Gold Exploitation

During the reign of Lord Nguyễn Phúc Nguyên, alluvial gold mining sites were established, employing thousands of laborers. At the same time, the Ty Kim Tuong was set up, comprising numerous gold-beating craftsmen responsible for gilding objects used in the royal court. The Nguyễn family also organized gold-panning households in the prefectures, known as Kim hộ. The number of Kim hộ and individuals engaged in gold mining and trading in Quảng Nam, Quy Nhơn, and Phú Yên reached tens of thousands.

The French merchant Pierre Poivre devoted a section of his writings to gold in the Quảng region, noting: “The famous gold mines belong to Dinh Chiêm (that is, the Quảng Nam administrative center), at a place called Phunrac, nearly eight leagues from Hội An... At the site where I personally observed, people occasionally found pure gold nuggets weighing about two ounces (0.28 g = 1 ounce)” (Poivre, 1884, pp. 324–337).

In the travel accounts of both Asian and European visitors, “gold always topped the list of products of

Đàng Trong” (Litana, 2017, p. 135). Like silk, during the winter season gold prices in Đàng Trong were relatively low. In Phủ biên tạp lục, Lê Quý Đôn wrote: “Gold is produced in the prefectures of Thăng Hoa (Quảng Nam), Quy Nhơn, and Phú Yên. In Quy Nhơn Prefecture, it is found in the hamlet of Ô Kim, which pays a separate levy, and in Trai Du (dầu chay), as well as in the hamlets and communes of Hà Thanh Diêm and Trung Chi in Đốc Sơ Commune” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 284).

In Phú Yên Prefecture, Kim hộ were located along the Ba River, in Cảnh Dương, Phúc Lộc, and Tân Dân. In the Quảng Nam region, Thăng Hoa Prefecture included “the Trà Nô and Trà Tế mountains at the headwaters of the Thu Bồn River in Duy Xuyên District, where gold is produced. In earlier times, gold vapors were strong, often winding through the earth; sometimes they rose straight upward, sometimes they flowed horizontally along streams to other mountains. Where gold was present, the soil was soft; where there was no gold, the soil was hard. The inhabitants went to the mountain foothills to locate the veins, excavated the soil, built shelters, piled the earth, and poured water over it; some pits were dug to depths of more than a thousand thước. After a day of washing, they often obtained gold dust filling a buffalo’s bladder, which was then delivered to the mining office for smelting and casting” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 286).

The headwaters of the Thu Bồn River at Trà Nô and Trà Tế contained abundant gold. In the Trà Nô area, rivers yielded more gold while mountains yielded less; in Trà Tế, the opposite was true. In addition, gold could also be extracted from the Chiên Đàn and Ô Da headwaters (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 286).

2.2.2. Sites of Agarwood Exploitation

Agarwood is a rare and valuable forest product found in deep forests and remote mountainous areas of Đàng Trong, such as Bồ Chính, Phú Yên, and Bình Định. However, agarwood used for trade and exchange with foreign countries was primarily sourced from Quảng Nam and Khánh Hòa. These two regions were the main suppliers of high-quality agarwood for export through Hội An trading port in the 17th–18th centuries.

Vast forested areas along the Trường Sơn mountain range, particularly in the districts of Nông Sơn, Tiên Phước, and Quế Trung in Quảng Nam, served as the principal sources of agarwood in Đàng Trong. Borri himself noted: “I would like to mention a type of wood regarded in many other places as the most precious commodity of Đàng Trong. That is agarwood (bois d’Aigle) and kỳ nam (Calambà), which are essentially the same but differ according to their properties. These tall and large trees are found in great numbers in the mountainous region of Kê Mọi” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 68).

The land of Khánh Hòa (Diên Khánh Prefecture) was renowned throughout Đàng Trong as a center of agarwood production. In Phủ biên tạp lục, Lê Quý Đôn wrote: “Kỳ nam agarwood produced at the mountain foothills of the communes in the two prefectures of Bình Khang and Diên Khánh in the Quảng region is of the finest quality; that from Phú Yên and Quy Nhơn

ranks second” (Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences – Institute of History, Lê Quý Đôn, 2019, p. 282).

In Khánh Hòa, Ninh Hòa and Vạn Ninh were two major agarwood-producing areas in Đàng Trong. The most famous was agarwood from Vạn Giã, the district capital of Vạn Ninh, as reflected in the saying: “Cassia trees grow among rocky ravines, and the agarwood of Vạn Giã spreads its fragrance through the mountains and forests” (Quách Tấn, 2019, p. 383). Tome Pires also observed: “The finest agarwood originates from the southern regions of Vietnam and is known as Calambac” (Pires, 1944, p. 113).

Kỳ nam was found in considerable quantities in the Vạn Giã area. In addition to its exquisite fragrance, kỳ nam was also a precious medicinal substance used to treat many serious ailments such as stroke, lockjaw, dysentery, asthma with phlegm, and various emergency conditions (Quách Tấn, 2019, p. 380).

Finding agarwood is an extremely difficult task; therefore, its value is very high. Agarwood seekers must spend long periods deep in the forest. In addition to preparing sufficient food supplies, they must also carry a type of medicinal plant known as ngải (ngải is a plant resembling turmeric or huỳnh tinh, about one thước tall, with a rhizome similar to galangal; its interior is slightly yellow and emits a camphor-like scent) (Quách Tấn, 2019, p. 384). When entering the forest to search for agarwood, seekers carried ngải to ward off snakes and protect themselves from poisonous winds and other dangers. They relied on detecting the fragrance and recognizing the distinctive form of the gió tree to locate agarwood. However, even when the scent was present, agarwood was not always found. Some seekers never returned from their expeditions, while others became lost in the forest. Although the work of collecting agarwood was extremely arduous and perilous, the strong demand for this commodity among foreign merchants compelled local people to brave the dangers and venture into the forests in search of agarwood.

2.3. The Role of Gold and Agarwood in Đàng Trong in the Economic Development of Hội An Trading Port in the 17th–18th Centuries

The Role of Gold

At Hội An trading port in the 17th–18th centuries, gold was one of the most valuable export commodities. The range of exported goods was extremely diverse. As contemporary sources observed: “Ships from Sơn Nam could purchase only one commodity, củ nâu; ships from Thuận Hóa could buy only pepper; but ships from Quảng Nam found no commodity that was unavailable” (Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences – Institute of History, 2007, p. 294). Another account noted: “There were so many goods that even a hundred large ships arriving at the same time could not carry them all” (Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences – Institute of History, 2007, p. 295).

Export commodities sent to China, Japan, Portugal, and other countries included gold, silk yarn, pearls, areca nuts, dried shrimp, bird’s nests, pineapple fiber, rice, ó wood, and agarwood (Lafont, 1990, p. 11). The presence of foreign merchants, together with “the establishment of trading factories and foreign

quarters,” contributed significantly to the flourishing economy of Hội An as a port city. Gold was traded extensively among international merchants, generating enormous profits for them. Alongside gold, various valuable timbers and forest products—such as rosewood, ironwood, sapanwood, cinnamon, and kỳ nam—were also traded at Hội An, further diversifying the range of export commodities (Poivre, 1884, p. 328).

Each year, around the beginning of the lunar calendar, Hội An entered its busiest trading season as merchant ships from many countries arrived in great numbers. Vietnamese traders brought local products such as raw silk, agarwood, gold, sugar, and cinnamon, while European ships carried porcelain, ceramics, paper, tea, silver ingots, and weapons. “Commercial transactions and exchanges continued for about six or seven months; once trading was completed, foreign merchants weighed anchor and departed, carrying the goods they had purchased on their return voyages” (Europeans in Annam, 2011, pp. 33–34).

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The trade in gold for export through Hội An trading port contributed significantly to the early formation and development of a commodity-based economy there. Hội An functioned not only as the place where almost all commercial exchanges between northern Đàng Trong and the outside world were conducted, but also as one of the most important stopovers along Far Eastern trade routes during this period (Nguyễn Thanh Nhã, 2017, p. 239). Gold was highly sought after by English, French, and Chinese merchants, who purchased it for resale in their home countries, generating substantial profits. Demand for gold and other commodities at Hội An also contributed to the emergence of several market towns with mixed urban–semi-urban characteristics such as Tam Kỳ, Nước Mặn, Kim Sơn, and An Thái—which maintained supportive relations with Hội An by regularly supplying goods (Phan Đại Doãn, 1990, p. 268). Gold thus became one of the commodities yielding considerable profits for both buyers and sellers.

Foreign trade played such a decisive role that, for the Nguyễn Lords, the measure of a good or bad year was not the agricultural harvest but rather the number of ships arriving in Đàng Trong within a year (Thích Đại Sán, 1963, p. 24). Due to historical conditions and the fact that the Nguyễn Lords did not monopolize gold extraction and trade, merchants and many other individuals at Hội An were able to accumulate significant wealth. High-quality gold was valued at 180 *lòi* per ingot (likely referring to strings of cash—translator’s note). Ch. B. Maybon observed that “trade at Hội An trading port yielded very large profits, with gold alone bringing returns of up to 33.5%” (Ch. B. Maybon, 1916, p. 334).

In addition, the Nguyễn Lords derived substantial revenue from taxes levied on gold mining in the prefectures of Quảng Nam, Quy Nhơn, and Phú Yên. *Kim hộ* operating at gold mining sites were required to pay annual taxes, such as “70 *lạng* from the Lỗ Đông source, and 38 *lạng*, 3 *đồng*, and 1 *phân* from the Thu Bồn source. Gold purchased in the Quảng region outside the period of international trade fairs was inexpensive;

when taken to Guangdong for sale, profits could reach 100%. Some individuals, such as Giang Thuyền, even purchased entire mountains, mined gold independently, and sold it widely,” and “brought it to Hội An port to sell to foreign merchants, earning no less than over one thousand *hốt* annually” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 227).

Because of the strong demand for gold trading, Hội An not only attracted foreign merchant vessels but was also selected by many countries as a location for establishing trading factories. “Hội An became a bustling and prosperous port city beginning in the 17th century. During this time, it was not only an important trading port of Vietnam but also a major commercial center

of Southeast Asia and a convenient stopover on Far Eastern maritime trade routes” (Vietnam Committee of Social Sciences – Institute of History, 1989, pp. 211–212).

Arising from the demand for gold trading at Hội An, the Nguyễn Lords paid close attention to this economic activity from an early period. Merchant ships from China, Japan, and Portugal arriving to purchase gold and other commodities were required to pay taxes to the Nguyễn Lords. For this reason, a specialized foreign trade administrative body was established in Đàng Trong at Hội An port. This agency, known as the *Ty Tàu Vụ* (Maritime Affairs Office), comprised 185 personnel, organized as follows:

Table 1.

Personnel of the Ty Tàu Vụ

(According to Nguyễn Chí Trung, 2010, *Cư dân Faifo–Hội An trong lịch sử*, Da Nang Publishing House, p. 137)

Position	Number (persons)
Chief of Ships (<i>Cai tàu</i>)	1
Deputy Chief (<i>Tri tàu</i>)	1
Registrar of Ships (<i>Cai bạ tàu</i>)	1
Supervisors (<i>Cai phủ tàu</i>)	2
Clerks (<i>Ký lục tàu</i>)	2
Gunner Guards (<i>Tấn thủ súng binh</i>)	60
Four naval squads	70
Interpreters (<i>Thông sự</i>)	7

Commercial exchange at Hội An trading port thus created employment for those serving in the *Ty Tàu Vụ*. In addition to this office, which directly oversaw trade activities at Hội An, the Nguyễn Lords also assigned “the Minh Hương, Hội An, Lao Chiêm communes, and Câu village to handle reporting and inspection duties” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 253). Annual tax revenues collected from Hội An trading port ranged from 10,000 to 30,000 *quan*, making a substantial contribution to the state treasury.

On Agarwood as a Commodity

Countries influenced by Buddhism and Islam highly valued agarwood, foremost among them China. Chinese merchants came to Hội An trading port to trade, and together with waves of Chinese migrants settling in Đàng Trong, they formed a bustling foreign merchants’ quarter (*phố khách*). Although they had arrived as early as the 17th century, it was after the mid-17th century—when the Ming dynasty was overthrown by the Manchu Qing—that immigration increased rapidly, resulting in the Chinese population coming to constitute the majority of Hội An’s urban residents.

The range of goods traded by the Chinese in Đàng Trong was diverse. They not only acted as merchants but also served as distributors, supplying goods to traders from other countries such as Japan, Portugal, Spain, England, and France. Chinese merchants collected goods in Hội An—including silk, cinnamon, pepper, musk, and especially agarwood and *kỳ nam*—to resell to shipowners of various nations. It can be said that the Chinese community at Hội An trading port became a key commercial force. With nearly 6,000 Chinese residents (Đỗ Bang, 1996, p. 74), they formed an important brokerage group in the agarwood trade, as

“the Chinese usually had abundant capital and were discreet” (Quách Tấn, 2019, p. 381).

The Japanese were also major traders at Hội An. As described in contemporary accounts, “at an annual market held at a seaport and lasting about four months, the Japanese brought on their ships goods worth four to five million silver coins, while the Chinese carried on their vessels—called *tam bản* boats—large quantities of fine silk and many other products from their country” (Đặng Trường, 2013, p. 44). Japanese merchants typically brought copper, sulfur, manufactured weapons, copper coins, cotton cloth, paper, saddles, and other items, with copper being the most profitable commodity. Goods that Japanese traders purchased at Hội An to take back to Japan included “sugar, areca nuts, pepper, agarwood, ceramics, silk, and others” (Đỗ Bang, 1996, p. 69).

The Portuguese arrived at Hội An trading port in the early 16th century. At that time, they came mainly to purchase “bird’s nests, agarwood, and silk textiles” (Đỗ Bang, 1996, p. 70). In the early 17th century, the Portuguese brought porcelain, ceramics, silver ingots, saltpeter, sulfur, lead, zinc, cloth, and blue and red felt. They purchased silk, precious woods, cinnamon, and sugar to ship to Macao or Malacca, while paying the highest commercial taxes among foreign traders (Đỗ Bang, 1996, p. 71).

Indian merchants also came to Hội An to buy agarwood, since Brahmins and Banian communities in India practiced cremation using highly fragrant wood, creating a constant demand for large quantities of agarwood. Export statistics show that forest, terrestrial, and marine specialty products accounted for 48% of total exports (Nguyễn Chí Trung, 2010, p. 137),

indicating that agarwood and kỳ nam made up a significant share of the export balance.

More importantly, taxes levied on foreign merchant ships trading—especially those purchasing agarwood and kỳ nam—were clearly specified:

Table 2. Export Taxes on Foreign Merchant Ships (According to Litana, Xứ Đàng Trong, Trê Publishing House, Ho Chi Minh City, 2017, p. 143)

Origin of merchant ships	Export tax
Shanghai	300 quan
Guangdong	300 quan
Fujian	200 quan
Hainan Island	50 quan
Japan	400 quan

This demonstrates that agarwood constituted a major export commodity with extremely high value. Consequently, agarwood and kỳ nam contributed enormous revenue to the development of the Đàng Trong economy—so much so that “a single ship fully loaded with this wood would provide a merchant with enough wealth to live comfortably for a lifetime” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 253).

Agarwood was not only a trade commodity but also a luxury forest product contributed to the Nguyễn Lords’ treasury: “According to the old regulations of the Nguyễn family, the regions were required to submit gold, silver, agarwood, and tortoiseshell, which were delivered to the inner palace and stored by the Tân Nhất naval guards” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 295). While agarwood could be freely traded, kỳ nam was reserved exclusively for the ruler due to “its renowned fragrance and efficacy” (Litana, 2017, p. 69).

Kỳ nam was a celebrated product that attracted many international merchants to Hội An with the primary aim of purchasing it for resale at high profit. Kỳ nam oil was a rare substance found only in certain parts of Southeast Asia and was the most famous and valuable product of Champa. It was described as follows: “Kỳ nam is black in color, rich in oil, and valued at 50 cruzados per catty among the Portuguese, whereas at the place of production it was worth its weight in silver—an equal amount of kỳ nam for an equal amount of silver” (Litana, 2017, p. 134).

Kỳ nam was especially prized for its extraordinary fragrance. Borri himself exclaimed: “At the place where kỳ nam is collected, this wood emits such a gentle and pleasant aroma that even when I buried a piece more than seven hand-spans deep underground, the scent could still be perceived” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 69).

From the 17th century onward, kỳ nam became one of the most important export commodities at Hội An trading port. Some Chinese merchants found it worthwhile to wait an entire year to accumulate sufficient quantities of kỳ nam to transport to Japan, because “at the collection site, kỳ nam cost 5 ducats per pound (approximately 450 g), but at Đàng Trong port it yielded no less than 15 ducats per pound, and once transported to Japan, its price rose to 200 ducats per pound” (Litana, 2017, p. 135).

Kỳ nam commanded extremely high prices in Đàng Trong: “In Quảng Nam, 100 cân was called one tạ; areca nuts cost 3 quan per tạ, pepper 12 quan per tạ,

whereas kỳ nam cost 120 quan per lượng; the price of agarwood varied widely” (Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences – Institute of History, 2007, p. 295).

The Japanese were particularly fond of kỳ nam, using it to make pillows when of sufficient size: “Instead of soft feather pillows, the Japanese used hard wooden headrests, and everyone sought to obtain a precious piece of wood. For kings and princes, only a kỳ nam wooden pillow was deemed worthy” (Cristoforo Borri, 2021, p. 69).

From the above analysis, it is clear that agarwood and kỳ nam played a central role in the export–import balance of Hội An trading port. Most notably, “total revenues from 1746 to 1752—when the number of ships arriving annually in Đàng Trong ranged between 80 (according to Kæmper, present from 1744 to 1753) and 60 (according to Poivre, present from 1749 to 1750). With an average tax of about 2,000 quan per ship, assuming 70 ships per year—a reasonable figure for the 1740s–1750s—the Nguyễn Lords would have collected approximately 140,000 quan annually” (Litana, 2017, p. 146). This suggests that tax revenue from foreign merchant ships exceeded revenues from other domestic taxes.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, gold and agarwood were exceptional commodities that played a crucial role in the economic development of Hội An trading port in the 17th–18th centuries. The distinctive nature of these export goods attracted merchant ships from many countries to engage in trade at Hội An, fostering the early emergence of a commodity-based economy in Đàng Trong. At this time, foreign trade assumed a role more significant than agriculture in Đàng Trong’s economy. Trade with countries around the world not only generated material wealth but also brought intellectual and cultural capital. Increased knowledge of neighboring countries and the desire to trade with them contributed to the unprecedented prosperity of Đàng Trong in general, and Hội An trading port in particular, during the 17th–18th centuries. As people and goods from Hội An were exported worldwide, they also stimulated the development of the region’s socio-cultural life.

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